

READING ANXIETY AND READING COMPREHENSION OF INDONESIAN UNIVERSITY EFL STUDENTS

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the relationship between foreign language reading anxiety and the reading performance STAIN Pamekasan EFL learners. This study also aimed to compare the level of reading anxiety between male student and female students. The data were collected from the sixth semester students majoring English Teaching and Learning Program of Tarbiyah Department, STAIN Pamekasan, Indonesia. The data were collected using Foreign Language Reading Anxiety Scale (FLRAS) which focuses to measure the level of anxiety in reading skill.. The data were analyzed using SPSS version 16 and Pearson Product Moment correlation is used to determine the degree of reading anxiety and Independent T-test is used to measure the significant difference between reading anxiety of male and female students. The results revealed that students experienced high reading anxiety and there is positive low correlation between reading anxiety level and reading comprehension. However, no significance difference was found between the level of foreign language reading anxiety between male and female students.

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1. Introduction

In teaching and learning of English as foreign language, it is important to master for language skills of reading, writing, listening, and speaking. Grabe and Stoller¹ argued that reading is considered as the most important language skills in second language acquisition since reading is central means learning new information and the primary means for independent learning. Regarding the importance of the reading skills, reading is taught as part of English subject since Junior High Scholl until university level in Indonesia. For university students, having good reading skill are necessary since most reputable journal as the good references for their courses are written in English as international language. Moreover, reading skill is also needed by junior and senior high school students since most of national examination questions are dealing with reading text. However, it was found that students' ability in reading was still low.²

The study about "Most Literate Nations In the World" conducted by Central Connecticut State University in 2016 placed Indonesia in 60th among 61 countries surveyed as the least interested in reading books.³ A National Socio-Economic Survey by Indonesia's Central Statistics Agency showed the country's TV audience reached 91.5% in 2015 while newspaper readers sat at 13.1%, the lowest point since 1984.⁴ It means that Indonesian prefer to watch/listen information than to read it. Besides, Indonesians low interest in reading is contrary to its interest in using internet in which the country is the sixth largest in the world in number of internet users.⁵ In this digital, learners tend to can consume everything on the internet from music, movies and videos on Youtube as well as their social media. The students read a lot from their social media from Facebook debates or Whatsapp chats, but they never really important subjects/book. Therefore, it is not surprisingly if reading skill of Indonesian is still need encouragement.

There are many factors which influence the failure of students to perform their English Skill. Skekahan stated that there are different factors influencing test takers' performance, including personality types, intelligence motivation, attitude, age, gender, and anxiety.⁶ Krashen also proposed motivation, self-confidence and anxiety as the affective factors failure in English

Language Learning.⁷ Among those factors, anxiety is considered as the crucial factors in Foreign Language Anxiety.⁸ Anxiety will provoke the feeling uneasiness which will interrupt the process of Second Language Acquisition.⁸ Anxiety, moreover, can happen pervasively in both inside and outside the classroom, preventing language learners from achieving a high level of L2 acquisition and thus resulting in large individual differences in second/foreign language acquisition.⁹

For many years, many language educators and researchers concern on the issue of anxiety in Second Language Acquisition and Foreign Language Acquisition. Razak, Yassin, and Rizan¹⁰ investigated the correlation of anxiety level and the academic achievement of 155 English Department students of Yemeni University. They also investigated the gender differences in the level of anxiety of those students. The study revealed that there is no significant correlation between the level of anxiety and the academic achievement of the students. The study also revealed that the anxiety level of female students is higher than male students but the difference between both genders are not significant. Gkonou¹¹ investigated the factors contributing to the creation and the increase of students' anxiety level in the class. The results of the research revealed anxiety can caused by input, language skills, the teacher, mistakes made in class, high reliance on marks, tests, and extrinsic motivation. In addition, both previous studies employ Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) which developed by Horwitz et al as the measurement instruments to measure the anxiety level.

Foreign language reading anxiety (FLRA) refers to the feelings of frustration and apprehension experiences by readers when they fail in comprehending a Second Language or Foreign language text.¹² In international context, several studies have been conducted on FLRA. Yet most of them address the relationship between reading anxiety and performance⁶, reading anxiety and reading strategy¹³, and reading anxiety and gender⁸.

Reading anxiety plays an important role in teaching learning process. However, Foreign Language (FL) teacher seldom neglected it. In Indonesian context there are some research related to reading anxiety but the subject is in Junior high school¹⁴ and Senior High School¹⁵. However, there had been relatively little research which had conducted related to reading anxiety of Indonesian EFL University students. Therefore, this study attempts to investigate the correlation between reading anxiety and reading proficiency and to examine FL reading anxiety across the gender

The purpose of this research is to give understanding about reading anxiety by assessing undergraduate students of The State Islamic Institute of Madura (STAIN Pamekasan). Thus, the research propose two research questions: 1) is there any correlation between students' reading anxiety level and their reading proficiency? 2) is there any difference in reading anxiety level among female and male students? To answer those questions, researcher will study undergraduate students of STAIN Pamekasan by using questionnaire to know students' reading anxiety level and to divide the students based on their gender and giving reading test to know students' reading proficiency.

2. Methodology

This research employs the quantitative approach with correlation research as the design. The research is to investigate the anxiety of Indonesian students toward reading comprehension in STAIN Pamekasan. The participant of this study are 124 students of 6th semester students who majoring English Teaching Learning program. The sixth semester students are chosen because they have been passed Reading I, Reading II, Reading III and Extensive Reading course in the previous semester. The distribution of the students based on gender can be seen on table 1

Table 1 : Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	82	66.1	66.1	66.1
Male	42	33.9	33.9	100.0
Total	124	100.0	100.0	

Foreign Language Reading Anxiety Scale (FLRAS) which proposed by Saito et al is utilized to measure the students reading anxiety.¹⁶ It consists of 20 items in which five-point values in Likert Scale were used. It ranges from strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree and strongly disagree. To measure students' reading comprehension, TOEFL reading section sample will be utilized. The reading test is taken randomly from TOEFL reading section prediction test. It consist of 3 passages with 30 multiple choice items. The correct answer will obtain 1 score and the wrong answer will get 0. Although the reading test items are taken from TOEFL reading section prediction test, The researcher still pilot the reading test since the reading test consist only 30 items and taken randomly from Longman TOEFL Book.¹⁷

To find out the relationship between reading anxiety and reading comprehension, the result of the FLRAS questionnaire and Reading comprehension test were computed using Pearson Product moment. This research will also divide the reading anxiety and reading comprehension across gender. Thus, the data were computed using independent t test. Those computations will use SPSS 16

Before distributed the reading test, the reading test items were piloted 30 university students excluded from the sixth semester students of STAIN Pamekasan. The reliability of the test is tested using KR 21. Rajab et al¹⁸ proposed that o determine the high level of anxiety, the mean value is set ranging from 1.00 to 3.00 and low level of anxiety will be determined based on the mean value ranging from 3.01 to 5.00.

3. Results and Findings

The aim of the study was to investigate the correlation between reading anxiety level and reading comprehension of EFL Indonesian University students who majoring English Language Teaching Program. The study also compares the Reading Anxiety level and Reading Comprehension of male and female university students. The researchers hypothesize that Reading Anxiety level have correlation with Students' Reading comprehension (Ha) and reading anxiety level are different among male and female students. The hypothesis was tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The data were collected from Questionnaire and Reading Test and computed by using SPSS.

The findings of the study are organized based on the following sub-topics

3.1. Reading Anxiety Level

The statistical descriptive was used to analyze the levels of reading anxiety and measure the reading anxiety level of University students. The result of the calculation is represented on Table 2.

Table 2 Reading Anxiety Level

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid High	97	78.2	78.2	78.2
Low	27	21.8	21.8	100.0
Total	124	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 shows that 78.2 % percent of the total participants have high level of reading anxiety while another 21.8 % percent have low level of reading anxiety. The reading anxiety level of the participants is categorized as high since the average mean obtained is 2.60. The results of

FLRAS indicate that the level of reading anxiety of English Language Teaching Program students of STAIN Pamekasan is high anxiety readers.

3.2. Reading Anxiety Level Based on Group

Table 3 Group Statistics Reading Anxiety Level of Female and Male Group

	Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Level_Ranxiety	Male	42	2.6762	.50076	.07727
	Female	82	2.5646	.50231	.05547

When comparing the level of reading anxiety between male and female groups, it is found that the mean value for male group is 2.67 and the mean value for female group is 2.56. Both group have high level of reading anxiety since the average score is lower than 3.00. However, the average value of reading anxiety level signifies that female group has higher reading anxiety level than the average value of male group. Furthermore, to test the significance different of reading anxiety level of both groups, independents sample T-test is carried out. From table 4, it is revealed that significant value between two groups is 0.794 which is higher than the predetermined alpha value (0.05). This result indicates that there is no significant different reading anxiety level between male and female participants.

Table 4: Independent Samples Test for Reading Anxiety Level of Male and Male Group

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means								
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Level_Ranxiety	Equal variances assumed	.069	.794	1.172	122	.244	.11156	.09521	-.07693	.30004
	Equal variances not assumed			1.173	82.992	.244	.11156	.09512	-.07763	.30074

3.3. Reading Anxiety and Reading Performance

For the purpose of this study, respondents' reading performance is measured by giving reading comprehension test which utilize TOEFL reading section sample. Based on the result of the reading comprehension test, it is found that the minimum score obtained by the students is 6.7 and the maximum score obtained by the students is 83.

Table 5 : Correlation between Level of Reading Anxiety and Score Of Reading Test

		Score_RAnxiety	Score_RComprehension
Score_RAnxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	.211*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.019
	N	124	124
Score_RComprehension	Pearson Correlation	.211*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.019	
	N	124	124

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Pearson Product Moment was carried out to determine whether there is correlation between Reading Anxiety and Reading comprehension. As shown in table 5, the Pearson r Correlation between two variables is 0.211. Based on Sarwono¹⁹, r value in range 0 – 0.25 is categorized very low. Therefore, the correlation between reading anxiety and reading comprehension of the participants of this present research is categorized very low. This result also reveals that Reading anxiety level has positive correlation to reading comprehension since the r value is positive. It means that the higher reading anxiety level of the participants will increase their reading comprehension. The significant (2-tailed) value of correlation is 0.019 which means that the correlation of both variables are significant since the significant (2-tailed) value is lower than 0.05. This indicates that students' reading anxiety level will have impact to their reading comprehension although the impact is very low. It means that students' reading comprehension will be higher if they experience anxiety.

4. Discussion

The result of FLRAS indicates that the level of reading anxiety of Students of English Teaching Learning Program of STAIN Pamekasan is high anxiety readers. The possible explanation to support this finding could be associated with participants' reading interest and the unfamiliar topic of reading text. In English Teaching and Learning program, students had been explored and exposed to the English reading materials. However, the exploration and the exposure just experience by the students in the course (teaching and learning process). The students only read the English text due to the course assignment. They have no willingness to read English text outside their English courses. This is line with the statement of ministry of education who stated that Indonesian' reading habit is still low because of a lack of passion.²⁰ The reading interest of students to read various topic outside English teaching learning reading materials is also so low that when they read the texts which unfamiliar for them, it will provokes students' anxiety. For that reason, they may feel highly anxious when they face unfamiliar topic of reading texts.

Furthermore, the present research also reveals that the female students have higher reading anxiety level than male students. However, the correlation of both gender are not significance. The findings is in line with the research conducted by Razak, Yassin, and Rizan¹⁰ in Yemeni University Student which also revealed that gender has no effect to determine level of reading anxiety.

Based on the result of Pearson product moment correlations, it was found that students' reading anxiety is related to their reading performance's score. The result indicates that r correlation coefficient is 0.211 which means that there is positive low correlation between students' reading anxiety and reading performance. In addition, the level of probability significance (sig.2-tailed) was 0.019 ($p= 0.019 < 0.05$) which indicates that the positive correlation between reading anxiety and reading performance is significant. It means that the higher participants' reading anxiety level experience, the better they perform on reading comprehension test. It can be concluded that the reading anxiety influenced the reading

performance of Students of English Teaching Learning Program of STAIN Pamekasan although the impact is low/weak. The plausible explanation to support this finding is that the participants of this present research are the students from sixth semester of English Teaching Learning Program of STAIN Pamekasan who have taken Reading I to Reading III and Extensive Reading in the previous semesters. On those courses, they have been trained and exposed to use various reading strategies. Furthermore, although the students experience reading anxiety, they can overcome the anxiety because the students have been equipped with adequate knowledge of reading strategies. So that the highly anxious readers still have adequate score of reading performance test.

Although, there is not much research on Foreign Language reading anxiety and Reading comprehension support this findings of the study. The researcher found that the result of this present study was in accordance with the research conducted by Joo & Damron²¹ who investigates reading anxiety of USA college students of Korean as Foreign Language and reading performance on Korean reading text reported there was a medium positive correlation between students' reading anxiety and students' reading performance. The result of Joo and Damron' study indicates that the more reading anxiety students had, the better reading performance they had on the reading test. This findings seems contrast with theories put by the previous researchers which found that reading anxiety have negative correlation with reading performance.^{22,23,6,8} Lastly, this study indicates that there is positive low correlation and influence reading anxiety and reading performance of students of English Teaching and Learning Program of STAIN Pamekasan.

This study limited the subject of the study only for sixth semester students of STAIN Pamekasan. Besides, the reading comprehension test used in this research is only 30 questions of TOEFL prediction sample which randomly took from Longman TOEFL book due to the time provided by the institution. In this study, the individual participants divided only by gender (female or male). Furthermore, further researchers are expected to explore the reading anxiety and different object of research such as the year of study, reading strategies, etc. The further researchers also can differentiate the subject based in the learning style or personality traits. The present research shows that reading anxiety could affect the learners in higher education even the learners majoring Englishh. Thus, teacher/lecturer should find strategies which can help decrease the students' reading anxiety.

5. Conclusion

Reading anxiety have major role on reading performance of students. Thus, the lecturer should encourage students to have good reading interest so that students are interested in reading various topic of text outside English teaching learning topic. Besides, in line with government' program to raise literacy culture of Indonesian students, lecturer can give special time for students to read a text outside the topic of E teaching and learning.

The major findings of this study are summarized as follows. First, the sixth semester students of English Teaching and Learning Program of IAIN Madura have high reading anxiety. Second, the female students experiences higher reading anxiety than that male students. However, the difference is not significant. The last, there is positive low correlation between reading anxiety and reading performance of students of English Teaching and Learning Program of IAIN Madura. The result indicated that the null hypothesis (Ho) is failed to be accepted and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) was accepted. It means that the higher participants' reading anxiety level, the better they perform on reading comprehension test.

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